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The Effect of Sustainability Reporting on Earnings Quality: Evidence from Non-Mediterranean Africa

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Abstract

Earnings quality is of significant interest to multiple stakeholders while sustainability reporting has been tipped as an apt ethical communication reflecting the firm's commitment towards resolution of sustainability concerns. The work sets out to produce empirical evidence from Non-Mediterranean Africa on the effect of sustainability reporting on earnings quality. The research design is ex-post facto while data was extracted from the published financial statement and sustainability reports or integrated reports of 10 quoted companies spanning natural resources, health care, oil and gas, consumer goods and industrial goods from Nigeria, Kenya and South Africa (2011 - 2020). Panel data regression was employed to analyze the data.

The study found that sustainability reporting significantly impacted earnings persistence but did not have a significant effect on accruals' quality and value relevance. Not only that, control variables exhibited positive associations with value relevance, even though these relationships lacked statistical significance. Leverage was linked to better accruals' quality and value relevance, although the effect was not statistically significant.

The study recommended that firms should step up their compliance level with the globally accepted requirements of sustainability reporting in the best interests of investors, regulators and multinational organizations.

Keywords: Sustainability Reporting, Earnings Quality, Legitimacy Theory

1. Introduction

The not-too-distant accounting scandals witnessed by big corporate entities such as Maxwell, Parmalat and Enron across the globe has inevitably called into question the worth of accounting information. Due to this phenomenon, stakeholders (regulators, investors, researchers, tax authorities, among others) in the world over have shown considerable interest in accounting information and earnings quality (Akintoye, Adegbe & Falayi, 2021). The quality of earnings implies the extent to which the earnings reported essentially reflects the underlying operations. Meanwhile, managers have latitude to choose from multiple accounting rules and principles. As a result, reported earnings may be at distance with the underlying economic fundamentals depending on their preferences.

Sustainability reporting is an amalgam of social, environmental, economic reporting alongside conventional financial reports. It typifies the communication of ethical commitment of the firm on her social, economic and environmental foot prints, in particular. A number of studies have concentrated on sustainability reporting in relation to value relevance of financial statement (Sutopo, Kot, Adiati & Ardila, 2018), reduction of information asymmetry (Al Natour, Meqbel, Kayed, & Zaidan, 2022), firm value (Loh, Thomas, & Wang, 2017), corporate earnings management (Joshua & Akintoye, 2022; Akintoye, Adegbe, & Falayi, 2021) and firm performance (Garg, 2015; Uwuigbe, Teddy, Uwuigbe, Emmanuel, Asiriwa, Eyitomi & Taiwo, 2018) with varied conclusions.

Review of relevant literature has, however, shown that there is no enough research focus on sustainability reporting and earnings quality. Besides, studies have been carried out on the effect or association of environmental reporting, a sub-set of sustainability reporting, on earnings quality leaving out other segments of sustainability reporting (Pereira, Monteiro, Silva, & Lima, 2023; Nangih, Emeka-Nwokeji, & Peters, 2022; Alipour, Ghanbari, Jamshidinavid, & Taherabadi, 2019) like social and economic aspects. However, Yalçin (2022) and Herlambang and Faisal (2022) respectively dwelled on the association between corporate sustainability performance and earnings quality in Turkey; and the effect of implementing integrated reporting on earnings quality in Indonesia. Findings from the studies produced divergent conclusions.

This paper takes a departure from the aforesaid focuses as well as biases and fills up observed gaps in existing literatures. It examines how sustainability reporting impacted the quality of earnings among corporate entities in Africa south of the Sahara.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Earnings Quality

The meaning of earnings quality has not gained wide and general acceptance or agreed measurement constructs among researchers. It is not discernible or determinable by mere review except when proxied on certain metrics for measurement. Earnings quality refers to the profit earned which totally reflects the financial activities in-built in the economic circumstances within the period under review (Healy & Wahlen, 1999). In the same line of thinking, Chan, Chan, Jegadeesh and Lakonishok (2006) cited in Mohammady (2010) see it as the extent to which earnings reported mirror the fundamentals of operations. Dechow and Schrand (2004) submit that earnings quality encompasses the present performance as well as information required for assessing the future. Menicucci (2020) views earnings quality from the perspectives of predictability, stability, informativeness, persistence, among others. Whereas, Dang and Pham (2022), from accounting and market perspectives, list seven attributes of earnings quality: stability, predictability, sustainability, cumulative quality, validity, prudence and timeliness.

Financial reporting, of which reported earnings is a key component, is commonly used for informed economic decision by managers, investors, analysts, regulators and standards setters (Perotti & Wagenhofer, 2014; Fonou-Dombeu, Mbonigaba, Olarewaju, & Nomlala, 2022). An apt summary of accounting information, high-quality earnings reflect accuracy, sustainability, predictability and fair value (Francis, Nanda & Olsson, 2008). Meanwhile, low-quality earnings typify earnings management and inaccuracies in accounting rules (Francis, Nanda & Olsson, 2008). Unreliable earnings quality exacerbates information asymmetry and brings about inefficient allocation of resources.

2.1.2 Sustainability Reporting

The conventional accounting system does not provide comprehensive information on the firm's economic, social and environmental footprints and the efforts at ensuring sustainability improvements (Schaltegger,

Etxeberria & Ortas, 2017). It dwells more on the financial aspect of the firm's operational activities leaving out crucial information gaps on other areas.

Sustainability reporting bridges the aforementioned shortcomings. It has been described as the ethical communication of the firm's commitment towards addressing the economic, social and environmental concerns of the stakeholders (Hahn & Kuhnen, 2013). It showcases the firm's buy-in into the global sustainable development template, is helpful in combating information asymmetry and discourages manipulation of earnings. Akintoye, Taiwo, and Owolabi (2020) consider sustainability reporting on a tripod: the environmental perspectives, governance issues and social concerns. The main objective of the firm is wealth maximization. Meanwhile, legitimacy and shareholders theories assert that this goal must not be attained without taking into cognizance the concerns of the stakeholders on the environment, economy, society and governance in decision making. Strategic management decision is all about efficient allocation of resources, Waddock and Graves (1997) suggest that organizations will achieve long term business performance objectives when sustainability reporting is internalized and embraced.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 The Legitimacy Theory

John Dowling and Jeffrey Pfeffer, in 1975, came up with legitimacy theory (Guthrie & Ward, 2006). The theory is built on the belief that the time-honoured value system of an organization should not be at variance with the value system (norms, values, beliefs, and definitions) of the larger society in which they operate and affirms that observed variance spells doom to the continued existence of the organization. It is assumed that the society and organizations subscribe to the same set of values, and couple with the fact that the firm derives her powers to access the resources of nature from the former and is therefore under obligations to deliver certain obligations to the satisfaction of the former (Shocker & Sethi, 1973; Dowling & Pfeffer, 1975; Deegan, 2002). The adverse consequence of non-adherence to the social contract is better imagined (Lindblom, 1993; Enerson & Adegbe, 2021). Suchman (1995) views legitimacy from three perspectives namely cognitive, moral and pragmatic; and points out that the success of an organization is hinged on how far the managers can address the threats and challenges inherent in legitimization issues.

Legitimacy theory is the pivot for many studies to present the rational explanations of why some firms have embraced practices such as integrated reporting, corporate social responsibility reporting and sustainability reporting to pander to societal expectations. The attraction of the theory lies in voluntary social and environmental disclosures of information not in strict compliance with prescribed statutory or regulatory obligations. In spite of its wide acceptance among researchers, legitimacy theory has been a subject of multiple criticisms. Legitimacy theory merely provides rational explanation of managerial behavior but fails to show how such behaviours stimulate transparency and accountability especially to stakeholders who are not capital providers (Owen, 2008) and does not present itself as a tool for making viable predictions (Mobus, 2005). The term social contract, which forms pivotal basis for the theory, is not easily defined, imprecise and opened to varied interpretations (Guthrie, Cuganesan & Ward, 2006; Deegan, 2000; O'Donovan, 2002). Additionally, societal expectations, in-built in social contract, are impermanent and do mutate over time (Guthrie, Cuganesan & Ward, 2006).

2.3 Empirical Review

Studies carried out in Turkey, Vietnam, Iran, Oman and Australia tend to suggest a positive link between Sustainability reporting and earnings quality. For instance, Khamesluei, Izadinia and Arabsalehi (2018) considered the effect of the level of sustainability disclosures on earnings quality among listed firms in the Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) from 2011 to 2016. While sustainability reporting as whole exerted significant and positive influence on the quality of earnings, environmental disclosures maintained positive and significant

link with earnings quality leaving out other components like social and economic dimensions which featured negative and significant effects.

Similarly, Yalçın (2022) worked on the association between corporate sustainability performance and earnings quality in Turkey based on 90 firm year observations from 2018 to 2020 fiscal years. The study discovered that sustainability performance influence on earnings quality was positive but low. However, the quality of earnings in relation to the environmental, social and governance elements of sustainability was insignificant. Meanwhile, in a study predicated on the Australian listed firms from 2002 to 2018, Jia and Li (2022) found that sustainability performance had a positive association with earnings persistence, among others.

Also, Dang *et al.* (2022) conversely explored how earnings quality drove sustainable reports in Vietnam among three hundred and twelve (312) companies. The study, which covered a period of five (5) years (2015 to 2019), revealed that earnings quality positively impacted sustainable reports during the review. The work of Al Wahaibi, Al Aamri, Al Rawahi, Al Shibli and Puthukulam (2023) on the degree to which corporate disclosure impacted earnings quality and fair financial reporting practices in companies produced a significant relationship between the examined variables. The empirical investigation made use of data derived from the external auditors of several listed companies in Oman using a structured questionnaire. Their study re-enforced the influence of corporate disclosure on earnings quality.

In the same vein, some scholars have reduced their investigation to the likely impact of an aspect of sustainability disclosures like environmental issues on earnings quality or its surrogates. These studies have established positive relationship between environmental reporting and the quality of earnings (Alipour *et al.*, 2019; Pereira *et al.*, 2023; Nangih *et al.*, 2022). Alipour *et al.* (2019) examined the link between environmental disclosure quality and earnings quality among one hundred and seven (107) non-financial firms in Iran. Data was mined from published statements for a period covering 2011 to 2016 and analyzed with panel data regression. Findings showed that environmental disclosure quality and earnings quality had significant positive association.

Pereira *et al.* (2023), also, in a study on thirty one (31) Portuguese firms from 2016 to 2020, considered to what extent did environmental sustainability reporting in association with indebtedness affect earnings quality. After deploying multiple linear regression analysis on the extracted data, the study concluded that the quality of earnings was positively influenced by the explanatory variables: environmental sustainability reporting and indebtedness.

In addition, Nangih *et al.* (2022) sampled six (6) quoted consumer goods entities in the Nigerian Exchange Group and examined the relationship between disclosures of the environment and the quality of earnings. The results pointed out that the effect of voluntary disclosures with respect to the environment in relation to earnings quality was not only positive but equally statistically significant.

Ha, Sibghatullah, Chae and Aldeehani (2022) singled out persistence as a proxy for earnings quality and studied the impact of environmental and social disclosure on it based on a sampled of one hundred and thirty six (136) quoted companies in Malaysia for upwards of eight years (2011 to 2018). It was established that environmental and social disclosures propelled the quality of earnings during the period under review.

Also, the effect of corporate social responsibility or corporate social discloses on earnings quality has been a subject of empirical review. The results therefrom have shown positive influence. In Vietnam, Khuong, Rahman, Meero, Anh, Liem, Thuy, and Ly (2022) undertook a study on what roles did corporate social responsibility pay in ensuring earnings quality among 76 listed companies. They found that corporate social responsibility as well as accounting comparability positively impacted earnings persistence.

Hoang, Abeysekera and Ma (2019), in Vietnam, examined how earnings quality drove corporate social disclosure with state and foreign ownership as moderating variables. The study, which was based on a sample of 133 firms from 2005 to 2011, concluded that the link between earnings quality and corporate social disclosure was not only positive but equally significant.

Beyond the studies of Khamesluei *et al.* (2018) which featured negative and significant effects of social and economic dimensions on earnings quality, other works aligned with their results. One of such is Souza, Flach, Borba and Broietti (2019) who explored to what extent socially responsible entities could produce quality financial reporting. Contrary to their expectation, they found out that sustainability reporting did not have relationship with financial reporting quality. Impliedly, low or high earnings quality was not rationally explained by sustainability reporting.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data and Sample Selection

The design of the research was *ex-post facto*. The work was on sustainability reporting and quality of earnings as practiced by large firms in Africa south of Sahara. We purposively sampled 10 quoted companies spanning natural resources, health care, oil and gas, consumer goods and industrial goods from Nigeria, Kenya and South Africa. We extracted data from published sustainability reports or integrated reports of the selected firms from 2011 to 2020.

Financial figures were extracted from the yearly financial reports and specific reports on sustainability alongside analysis of the contents of the respective reports. The level of compliance with respect to disclosures on sustainability was measured against the metrics provided by the Stock Exchanges in the countries concerned and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). A scale ranging from 1 to 5 was created to weigh the deepness of the disclosed information.

3.2 Specification and Definition of Models

We submit that earnings quality depends on sustainability reporting while making use of firm size and leverage as moderating variables. The study proxied earnings quality in terms of earnings persistence, accrual quality and value relevance following prior studies: (Hoang, Abeysekera & Ma, 2019; Kareem Al Ani, 2021; Alipour, Ghanbari, Jamshidinavid & Taherabadi, 2019). Again, we viewed sustainability reporting in terms of environmental sustainability reporting, economic sustainability reporting, social sustainability reporting and corporate governance sustainability reporting in terms of the environment, economy, society and governance. (Akintoye, Adegbe & Falayi, 2021).

Earnings Persistence Model 1

$$EP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ENVR_{1it} + \beta_2 ECONR_{2it} + \beta_3 SOCR_{3it} + \beta_4 COGR_{4it} + \beta_5 FS5_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{6it} + \mu_{it}$$

Accruals Quality Model 2

$$AQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ENVR_{1it} + \beta_2 ECONR_{2it} + \beta_3 SOCR_{3it} + \beta_4 COGR_{4it} + \beta_5 FS5_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{6it} + \mu_{it}$$

Value Relevance Model 3

$$VR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ENVR_{1it} + \beta_2 ECONR_{2it} + \beta_3 SOCR_{3it} + \beta_4 COGR_{4it} + \beta_5 FS5_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{6it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where

EP = Earnings Persistence

AQ= Accruals Quality

VR= Value Relevance

ENVR = Report on Environmental Sustainability Reporting

ECONR = Report on Economic Sustainability Reporting
 SOCR = Report on Social Sustainability Reporting
 COGR = Report on Corporate Governance Sustainability Reporting
 FMZ= Firm Size
 LEV = Leverage
 μ_{it} = error term
 β_0 = intercept or the constant
 $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = denote the coefficient of explanatory variables
 $\beta_5 - \beta_6$ = denote the coefficient of control variables

Table 1. Measurement of Variables

Earnings Quality - Dependable Variables			
Measure	Abbreviation	Definition	Existing Literature
Earnings Persistence	EP	<p>Persistence is regarded as the amount of the current earnings that will be replicated in the future from year to year.</p> $\frac{\text{Earnings}_{i,t}}{\text{Total Asset}_{i,t-1}} = \alpha + \beta_1 \frac{\text{Earnings}_{i,t-1}}{\text{Total Asset}_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$ <p>Where: i = firm t = year Earnings_{i,t} = current year's net income before extraordinary items $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ = the residuals β_1 = earnings is highly persistent where the value is close to one (1) and not persistent where the value is close to zero (0). Users of accounting information identify highly persistent earnings as worthwhile, less temporary, and more stable (Richardson, Sloan, Soliman & Tuna, 2001).</p>	Boonlert-U-Thai, Meek and Nabar (2006); Ali, Chen, and Radhakrishnan (2007); An (2017).
Accruals Quality	AQ	<p>Dechow and Dichev (2002) and Mikhail, Walther and Willis (2003) submit that earnings quality is high when future cash flows contain lower estimation error of accruals. The following equation derived by Francis, LaFond, Olsson and Schipper (2005) is adopted in this study:</p> $\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{TCA}_{i,t}}{\text{TotalAssets}_{i,t-1}} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \frac{\text{OCF}_{i,t-1}}{\text{TotalAssets}_{i,t-1}} + \beta_2 \frac{\text{OCF}_{i,t}}{\text{TotalAssets}_{i,t-1}} \\ & + \beta_3 \frac{\text{OCF}_{i,t+1}}{\text{TotalAssets}_{i,t-1}} + \beta_4 \frac{\Delta\text{REV}_{i,t}}{\text{TotalAssets}_{i,t-1}} \\ & + \beta_5 \frac{\text{PPE}_{i,t}}{\text{TotalAssets}_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned}$ <p>i= the firm TCA = current year's total current accruals OCF= operating cash flow ΔREV=the change in operating revenue PPE= property, plant and equipment</p>	Francis, LaFond, Olsson and Schipper (2005); An (2017).
Value Relevance	VR	<p>Value relevance connotes the predictable link between accounting disclosure and equities' market values</p>	Collins, Maydew and Weiss (1997); Ali and Hwang (2000); An (2017).

		$P_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BV_{it} + \beta_2 EPS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$ <p>Here, <i>i</i> and <i>t</i> represent the firm and year respectively. While the end of year's stock price is P_{it}, the end of year' book value of stock is BV_{it}. Additionally, the end of year's earnings per share is represented by EPS_{it} and the residuals is taken as ϵ_{it}.</p> <p>Statistically, the explanatory power of regression (R^2) in the above equation constitutes the value-relevance. Large R^2 implies more value relevant earnings while small R^2 represents less value relevant earnings.</p>	
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Sustainability Reporting – Independent Variables

Measure	Definition	Existing Literature
Environmental, Economic Social, and Corporate Governance Reporting	The arithmetic mean of the scores for each indicator under the sustainability reporting metrics.	Loh, Thomas and Wang (2017); Ching, Gerab and Toste (2017); Akintoye, Adegbe and Falayi (2021).

Control Variables			
Measure	Abbreviation	Definition	Existing Literature
Firm Size	FMZ	Natural logarithm of total assets	Alipour, Ghanbari, Jamshidinaid and Taherabadi (2019)
Leverage	LEV	Ratio of total debt to total assets	

Source: Compiled by the Authors, 2024

4. Results and Discussions

The analysis starts with descriptive statistics. This is important as it helps in knowing the features and how the variables behave prior to the main estimation technique. The interaction between mean and median is used to explain how skewed the variables are. The average mean value above the median value explained the reasons for the positive skewness. This means that earnings persistence (EP), value relevance (VR), economic responsibility (ECONR), environmental responsibility (ENVR), leverage (LEV), and firm size (FMZ) are all positively skewed. The negative skewness is caused by the interaction between mean values that is less than the median value. Therefore, accrual's quality (AQ), social responsibility (SOCR), and corporate governance responsibility (CONGR) are negatively skewed. This implies that the variables have long right and long left tails.

The standard deviation explains the dispersion from the average mean. The study showed that a value relevance of 7203.82 has the highest S.D., followed by a leverage of 4.9804, while the least is accounted for by an accrual quality of 0.0876. Furthermore, kurtosis helps in explaining whether the variables are normally distributed. It showed that only earnings persistence is mesokurtic, as the value is very close to 3. Other variables were both platykurtic and leptokurtic in nature, as their values were rather below or above the benchmark of 3. More explanation of the normal distribution of the variables is explained using the probability of Jarque-bera, and it showed all variables, except for ENVR, are not normally distributed at the 5% level of significance. The total observation of the data is 100.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	EP	AQ	VR	ECONR	ENVR	SOCR	COGR	LEV	FMZ
Mean	0.833500	-0.03164	2376.991	3.250000	2.952100	4.132400	3.149000	2.661700	76901111
Median	0.730000	-0.02597	122.0000	3.000000	2.570000	4.330000	3.170000	1.230000	37717220
Std. Dev.	0.473522	0.087651	7203.823	0.849837	1.198755	0.789259	0.851753	4.980496	1.14E+08

Skewness	0.837672	-0.4498	3.605172	3.799079	0.306241	-0.84798	-0.65270	6.189617	2.949952
Kurtosis	2.912811	5.123024	15.55388	30.43731	2.068470	2.447696	2.626717	49.71352	11.80307
Jarque-Bera	11.72659	22.15213	873.2875	3377.241	5.178676	13.25552	7.680904	9730.827	467.9289
Probability	0.002842	0.000015	0.000000	0.000000	0.075070	0.001323	0.021484	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	83.35000	-3.1638	237699.1	325.0000	295.2100	413.2400	314.9000	266.1700	7.69E+09
Sum Sq. Dev.	22.19808	0.760581	5.14E+09	71.50000	142.2645	61.67002	71.82290	2455.729	1.29E+18
Observations	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Authors’ Computation using EViews 10, 2024

Correlation results between variables help the researcher in knowing how strong, weak, or moderate variables are correlated, and it also helps in knowing whether there is a problem of multicollinearity in the series, especially among the independent variables. Table 3 presents the outcome of the correlation of independent variables with dependent variables. In respect to earnings persistence, the study found that a SOCR of 0.6785 and a COGR of 0.6170 had a strong positive correlation with earnings persistence. ECONR 0.2968 and ENVR 0.3859 have a weak positive correlation with earnings persistence, while control variables such as LEV of -0.0361 and FMZ of -0.0896 have a weak negative correlation with earnings persistence. Regarding accrual’s quality, the study found that all variables, except for the LEV of 0.0564, have a weak negative correlation with accrual’s quality. While all variables have a weak negative correlation with value relevance, except for the SOCR of -0.5829, which has a moderately weak correlation with value relevance.

Therefore, the study found that while sustainability reporting has a positive correlation with earnings persistence, it has a negative correlation with accruals' quality and value relevance. On multicollinearity, except for corporate governance, which has a value of 0.9159 in correlations with social reporting, other variables have values that are moderate, thereby ruling out the problem of multicollinearity among variables.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	<i>EP</i>	<i>AQ</i>	<i>VR</i>	<i>ECONR</i>	<i>ENVR</i>	<i>SOCR</i>	<i>COGR</i>	<i>LEV</i>	<i>FMZ</i>
EP	1								
AQ	-0.250209	1							
VR	-0.255333	0.085540	1						
ECONR	0.296880	-0.206911	-0.153885	1					
ENVR	0.385942	-0.123038	-0.320713	0.351417	1				
SOCR	0.678572	-0.254426	-0.582938	0.352881	0.561086	1			
COGR	0.617050	-0.233493	-0.473439	0.388110	0.791984	0.915930	1		
LEV	-0.036135	0.0564145	-0.071882	-0.109867	-0.125307	0.048552	-0.034249	1	
FMZ	-0.089630	-0.131192	-0.084254	-0.048168	-0.069568	0.217346	0.229777	0.089391	1

Source: Authors’ Computation using EViews 10, 2024

Objective One

To examine the effect of sustainability reporting on earnings persistence, the study first engages a residual cross-section dependence test to determine if the data collected from cross-sectional observations are independent of each other. This is necessary in a panel regression estimate, as the interdependence of variables in panel regression can affect the validity of the test. The study employed Breusch pagan LM, Pesaran scaled LM, and Pesaran CD tests. The rule of thumb is that the p-values of these tests at least one must be greater than

5% level of significance. As presented in Table 4, the study found that two out of the tests have p-values that are greater than the 5% level of significance. This evidences that the variables are not interdependent.

Table 4: Residual Cross Section Dependence Test A

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	61.64613	45	0.0501
Pesaran scaled LM	1.754656		0.0793
Pesaran CD	-0.132266		0.8948

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2024

The outcome of the effect of sustainability reporting on earnings persistence is presented in Table 5. The result showed that the lag value of EP (-1) of 0.8258 was positively, and its corresponding p-value of 0.0000 was below the 5% level of significance. This implies that when other variables are held constant, a percentage increase in the lag value of earnings persistence would positively and significantly impact its current value (EP) to the tune of 83.58%. Furthermore, the study found that ECONR of 0.0261, ENVR of 0.0107, SOCR of 0.1477, and FMZ of 0.0073 positively impacted earnings persistence, while COGR of -0.1334 and LEV of -0.0048 negatively impacted earnings persistence. The significance level of each variable showed that only the SOCR p-value of 0.0447 was below the 5% level of significance, while other variable p-values were above the 5% level of significance. Therefore, by implication, a percentage increase in ECONR, ENVR, SOCR, and FMZ would boost earnings persistence to the tune of 2.61%, 2.07%, 14.77%, and 0.733%, respectively. On the other hand, a percentage increase in COGR and LEV would reduce earnings persistence to the tune of 13.34% and 0.048%.

The R², adjusted R², F-statistic, and probability all explain the model as a whole. From table 5, the coefficient of determination, denoted as R² of 0.9238, explained that independent variables, i.e., sustainability reporting, accounted for 92.38% of the variation in the dependent variable (EP), while the fraction of 7.62% is explained by other factors not included in the model. This position was further confirmed by the adjusted R² of 91.73%, which truly shows the behaviour of the dependent variable according to the number of variables in the model. Hence, both explained the good fit of the model and asserted that sustainability reporting is a great predictor of earnings persistence. The F-statistic of 142.1357 and its p-value of 0.0000 explained that the model is statistically significant to explain the relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings persistence of the selected firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. Furthermore, the result of the Jarque-Bera test, which explained whether the residual of the regression model in terms of skewness and kurtosis is normally distributed, showed that the probability of 0.3611 is higher than the 5% level of significance. This implies that the residual of the regression is normally distributed.

**Table 5: Pooled Panel Regression
Dependent Variable: EP**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EP(-1)	0.825853	0.052734	15.66065	0.0000
ECONR	0.026140	0.033388	0.782902	0.4359
ENVR	0.010740	0.020410	0.526231	0.6001
SOCR	0.147751	0.072473	2.038719	0.0447
COGR	-0.133410	0.090125	-1.480310	0.1426
LEV	-0.004810	0.002880	-1.670510	0.0986
FMZ	0.007301	0.009559	0.763776	0.4472
C	-0.302530	0.196523	-1.539390	0.1276
R ² =0.9238	Adj-R ² =0.9173	F-Stat=142.1357	Prob=0.0000	
JBT	2.0368			
Prob	0.3611			

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2024

Objective Two

The second objective looked into the relationship between sustainability reporting and the accrual quality of the selected firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. Just like the first objective, the study carried out a cross-sectional dependence test to determine whether variables are interdependent on each other. Table 6 shows the outcome of the test. The study employed Breusch pagan LM, Pesaran scaled LM, and Pesaran CD tests. The rule of thumb is that the p-values of these tests at least one must be greater than 5% level of significance. As presented in Table 6, the study found that the three tests have p-values that are greater than the 5% level of significance. This evidences that the variables are not interdependent.

Table 6: Residual Cross Section Dependence Test B

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	51.98933	45	0.2203
Pesaran scaled LM	0.736741		0.4613
Pesaran CD	-1.17331		0.2407

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2024

Table 7 presents the pooled panel regression of the effect of sustainability reporting on accrual's quality in the selected sub-Saharan Africa. The study revealed that the lag value of asset quality, i.e., AQ (-1) of 0.0068, was positively signed, with a p-value of 0.9540 not statistically significant at the 5% level. This implies that a percentage increase in the lag value of an accrual's quality would bring about a 0.068% increase in the current value of the accrual's quality when other variables in the model are held constant. Although this value was not statistically significant,

Moreso, the study further found that while ECOR of -0.0215, SOCR of -0.0506, and FMZ of -0.0087 have negative effects on accrual's quality, ENVR of 0.0026, COGR of 0.0407, and LEV of 0.0021 have positive effects on accrual's quality. Checking on the significant level of each variable, findings showed that only the FMZ p-value of 0.044 is below the 5% level of significance, while others are above this benchmark. By implication, a percentage increase in ECOR, SOCR, and FMZ would bring about 2.15%, 5.06%, and 0.087% decreases in accrual's quality, while a percentage increase in ENVR, COGR, and LEV would bring about 0.026%, 4.07%, and 0.021% increases in accrual's quality.

On the whole model, the study found that independent variables jointly accounted for 41.61% of the variation in the dependent variable, while a fraction of 58.39% was accounted for by variables not considered in the model. The adjusted R² of 34.92% confirmed the true behaviour of the dependent variable based on the number of variables included in the model. This explained why sustainability reporting weakly predicts an accrual's quality. The significance of the model is explained using the F-statistics and its probability. Findings showed that the F-statistic of 3.2311 and its p-value of 0.0044 explained that the model is highly statistically significant to explain the effect of sustainability reporting on the accrual's quality of the selected firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. In addition, the probability result of the Jarque-Bera test of 0.7287 is higher than the 5% level of significance. This implies that the residual of the regression is normally distributed.

Table 7: Pooled Panel Regression
Dependent Variable: AQ

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
AQ(-1)	0.006833	0.117615	0.058100	0.9540
ECONR	-0.021509	0.019509	-1.102506	0.2735
ENVR	0.002688	0.013081	0.205508	0.8377
SOCR	-0.050649	0.034845	-1.453570	0.1499
COGR	0.040706	0.050581	0.804760	0.4233

LEV	0.002104	0.001149	1.831370	0.0707
FMZ	-0.008768	0.004286	-2.045751	0.0440
C	0.256283	0.105644	2.425911	0.0175
R ² =0.4161	Adj-R ² =0.3492	F-Stat=3.2311	P-Value=0.0044	□
JBS	0.6329			
Prob	0.7287			

Source: Authors’ Computation using EViews 10, 2024

Objective Three

The third objective investigates the contribution of sustainability reporting to the value relevance of the selected firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. Just like other objectives, a residual cross-section dependence test was done, and the results are presented in Table 8. The result showed that the Breusch Pagan test, Pesaran Scaled LM test, and Pesaran CD test have p-values of 0.0007, 0.0001, and 0.0000, respectively, which are below the 5% level of significance. This result suggests the presence of cross-sectional dependence among the variables. Hence, the standard pooled regression estimate may not be appropriate to estimate this model, and as such, the study employed a robust least regression test instead.

Table 8: Residual Cross Section Dependence Test B

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	81.43607	45	0.0007
Pesaran scaled LM	3.840699		0.0001
Pesaran CD	6.62022		0.0000

Source: Authors’ Computation using EViews 10, 2024

The results of the robust least regression are presented in Table 9. The study revealed that the lagged value of value relevance, i.e., LVR(-1) of 0.9307, positively impacted its current value, and the p-value of 0.0000 is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. This implies that, while holding other variables constant, a lagged value of relevance would bring about a 93.07% increase in its current value, ceteris paribus. More importantly, the coefficients of other variables in the model showed that ECONR of 0.1968, COGR of 0.0546, LEV of 0.0070, and FMZ of 0.0136 have positive effects on value relevance, while ENVR of -0.0387 and SOCR of -0.1832 have negative effects on value relevance. However, none of the variables have p-values below the 5% level of significance. By implication, a percentage increase in ECONR, COGR, LEV, and FMZ would bring about 19.68%, 4.46%, 0.07%, and 1.3697% increase in value relevance, while a percentage increase in SOCR and COGR would bring about 3.87% and 18.32% decrease in value relevance of the sampled corporate entities in Africa south of Sahara.

The study also explained the joint effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable using the coefficient of determination. It was found that R² of 0.8018 explained that sustainability reporting jointly causes about 80.8% variation in value relevance, while the fraction of 19.82% was accounted for by other factors not included in the model. The adjusted R² of 78.48% further explained that the independent variables were able to predict the dependent variable based on the number of variables included in the model. The significance of the model was explained using the F-statistic and its p-value result. It was found that the F-statistic of 2665.71 and its p-value of 0.0000 suggest that the model has a good fit and is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that the model is significant in explaining the contribution of sustainability reporting to the value relevance of the selected firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. In addition, the p-value of Jargue-bera of 0.6501 suggests that the residual of the regression is normally distributed.

Table 9: Robust MM-Estimation Regression
Dependent Variable: LVR

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
LVR(-1)	0.930734	0.02931	31.75523	0.0000
ECONR	0.196854	0.159084	1.237418	0.2159
ENVR	-0.038731	0.083631	-0.463122	0.6433
SOCR	-0.183208	0.202495	-0.904754	0.3656
COGR	0.054673	0.293642	0.186191	0.8523
LEV	0.007070	0.008432	0.83842	0.4018
FMZ	0.013697	0.02992	0.457802	0.6471
C	0.191051	0.608876	0.313777	0.7537
R2=0.8018	Adj-R2=0.7848	Rn-SqStat=2665.71	Prob=0.0000	
Jarque-Bera	0.8611			
Prob	0.6501			

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2024

5. Discussion of Findings and Implications

This study examined the effect of sustainability reporting on the earnings quality of the selected firms in Sub-Saharan Africa, spanning 2010 to 2019. Three models were specified in line with the objectives of the study. Therefore, earnings quality was measured using earnings persistence, accruals' quality, and value relevance. The sustainability reporting was measured using the four major aspects of sustainability, such as economic, social, environmental, and corporate governance, while leverage and log of firm size were control variables included in the models. Panel data were sourced from the annual financial accounts of the selected 10 firms in Sub-Saharan Africa, and the data were estimated using standard pooled regression and robust least regression, while the descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and residual cross-section dependence test were supportive tests used in this study.

The findings revealed that while ECONR, SOCR, and ENVR responsibility have a positive effect on earnings persistence, ENVR and COGR have a positive effect on accrual's quality, and ECONR and COGR have positive effects on value relevance. More so, while sustainability reporting significantly impacted earnings persistence, it impacted insignificantly on accruals' quality and value relevance. More importantly, the effects of control variables were positive on value relevance, though they are insignificant. On accruals quality, it was leverage that has positive effect but the effect was insignificant. However, the effect of FMZ was negative on earnings persistence, while leverage was positive and insignificant.

Based on these findings, the study submitted that sustainability reporting significantly impacts earnings persistence but does not have a significant effect on accruals' quality and value relevance. Not only that, control variables exhibit positive associations with value relevance, even though these relationships lack statistical significance. Leverage is linked to better accruals' quality and value relevance, although the effect is not statistically significant.

Our conclusion in respect of earnings persistence is in consonance with the findings of the previous works of the following researchers: Ha *et al.*, (2020); Khuong *et al.*, (2022); Jia *et al.*, (2022) and Pereira *et al.*, (2023). Meanwhile, sustainability reporting does not have a significant effect on accrual quality and value relevance. Thus, the findings of this study do not support prior discoveries of Jeriji and Nasfi (2023) and Thompson, Ashimwe, Buertey and Kim (2022) which establish that sustainability reporting has a significantly positive relationship with the firm value. Similarly, empirical studies of Kareem AL Ani (2021) demonstrate that a significantly positive connection exists between corporate social responsibility disclosure and value relevance. Echobu, Ekundayo and Abu (2022), in their study on value relevance of sustainability reporting, find out that social sustainability report is value relevant.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study sets out to investigate the influence of sustainability reporting on earnings quality among selected multinational firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. Sustainability reporting as an independent variable was further

divided into environmental sustainability reporting, economic sustainability reporting, social sustainability reporting and corporate governance sustainability reporting. Main features of earnings quality such as earnings persistence, accruals quality and value relevance stood for dependent variables.

The results have shown that sustainability reporting significantly impacts earnings persistence but does not have a significant effect on accrual quality and value relevance. From these results, it is clear that sustainability strengthens earnings persistence. Investors and financial institutions desiring earnings persistence should look out for firms that have internalized sustainability reporting in their quest for sustainability.

Nevertheless, sustainability reporting does not have a significant effect on accrual quality and value relevance among the sampled firms. Divergence in accounting practices and depth of compliance with Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) across the countries may have been responsible. Granting the dominant interest of investors in accrual quality and value relevance, firms should step up their compliance level with the globally accepted requirements of sustainability reporting.

This paper enriches the literature with empirical evidence on the effect of sustainability reporting on earnings quality amongst listed firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. Future researches should focus on other continents to give room for robust comparison between continents across the world.

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